

JURISPRUDENCE

IMPLICATIONS OF EU'S ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE ACT

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Abstract

On December 8, 2023, the members of the Council of the EU, together with the negotiators of the European Parliament, reached a temporary agreement on the proposal of the Harmonized Rules on Artificial Intelligence (AI Act), in order to regulate the use of artificial intelligence in the European Union. This comes more than five years after the EU Council made its first call for rules and regulations on artificial intelligence. The AI Act is expected to set global standards for regulating the use of AI in the same way that the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) did for the protection of personal data. This paper reviews the timeline of AI Act proposal, as well as expected implications of it, both from the legal and practical aspects. The expected new obligations of providers of services based on artificial intelligence, especially large language models (LLM) for general purposes, permitted and prohibited ways of training those systems, acceptable and unacceptable use of systems based on artificial intelligence, the rights and obligations of users, as well as physical persons in relation to those systems, were discussed.

Keywords: AI Act, large language models, EU, artificial intelligence, regulation, EU Council, EU Parliament.

INTRODUCTION

December 8th, 2023 will be remembered as one of most important days in efforts to systematically regulate artificial intelligence in the EU. On that day, the members of the Council of the EU, together with the negotiators of the European Parliament, reached a temporary agreement on the proposal of the Harmonized Rules on Artificial Intelligence, known in public simply as AI Act (further in this paper: Act), more than five years after the EU Council made its first call for rules and regulations on artificial intelligence usage.

The proposed Act adopts a risk-based approach, in which AI systems are classified and regulated based on individual or collective risks to citizens. The Act deals with AI on technology-neutral ground, meaning that any technological solution that uses AI principles will be subject to it ([11]).

The European Commission, in April 2021, proposed the first EU regulatory framework for AI Act ([7]). During following two and a half years, a lot was done towards adopting a comprehensive regulation in this field. The aim of this paper is to familiarize the reader with these efforts, to present initiatives and their outcomes, and, most importantly, to present the expected implications of the Act once it gets adopted. We will use the current version of the Act proposal, which means that some parts of it may be slightly changed in the final, applicable version once adopted, but this is not very likely to happen.

THE PATH TOWARDS the adoption of ACT's final proposal

The question of adopting the regulation on artificial intelligence formally started in April 2018, when the European Commission published its communication named *Artificial Intelligence for Europe*. The full name of this letter is *Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the European Council, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the regions - Artificial*

Intelligence for Europe ([9]). This document was the starting position for EU institutions.

Before 2018, there were also some informal initiatives towards regulating AI usage. For example, in May 2017, the Commission published its mid-term review of the Digital Single Market strategy. It highlighted the importance of building on Europe's scientific and industrial strengths, as well as on its innovative startups, to be in a leading position in the development of AI technologies, platforms, and applications.

Also, the European Council, in 2017, stated that the EU needs a sense of urgency to address emerging trends such as AI "while at the same time ensuring a high level of data protection, digital rights and ethical standards. The Council here invited the Commission to put forward a European approach to artificial intelligence ([13]).

After that, about one year after the mentioned Communication from April 2018, in April 2019, Independent AI High-Level Expert Group presented *Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence* ([17]). This significant document defines *trustworthy AI*, contains guidelines for implementing it and deals with several crucial fields where AI can make a great (positive and, in the same time, negative) influence. These are the respect for human dignity, freedoms of the individual, the respect for democracy, justice and the rule of law, equality, non-discrimination and solidarity, as well as citizens' rights.

Furthermore, this documents defines the minimum requirements for acceptable usage of AI. More precise, the Guidelines state that AI should be mandated to comply with these 4 principles: (1) respect for human autonomy, (2) prevention of harm, (3) fairness and (4) explicability. As Group wisely concludes, *tensions may arise between the above principles, for which there is no fixed solution. In line with the EU fundamental commitment to democratic engagement, due process and open political participation, methods of accountable*

deliberation to deal with such tensions should be established ([17], pp 15).

The Group also points out the basic requirements for the trustworthy AI:

- (1) Human agency and oversight - including fundamental rights, human agency and human oversight;
- (2) Technical robustness and safety - including resilience to attack and security, fall back plan and general safety, accuracy, reliability and reproducibility;
- (3) Privacy and data governance - including respect for privacy, quality and integrity of data, and access to data;
- (4) Transparency - including traceability, explainability and communication;
- (5) Diversity, non-discrimination and fairness - including the avoidance of unfair bias, accessibility and universal design, and stakeholder participation;
- (6) Societal and environmental wellbeing - including sustainability and environmental friendliness, social impact, society and democracy;
- (7) Accountability - including auditability, minimisation and reporting of negative impact, trade-offs and redress.

On February 19th, 2020, the European Commission published a *White paper on Artificial Intelligence* ([12]). This document's main value is the presented legal framework for developing and utilizing AI: this part of the whitepaper, named *An ecosystem of trust: regulatory framework for AI*, consists of 8 sections which prescribe the wanted directions in developing, training and using AI, identifies opportunities and problems, and imposes the recommendations to various state and non-state actors in the AI problematics. These sections are:

- (1) Problem definition;
- (2) Possible adjustments to existing EU legislative framework relating to AI;
- (3) Scope of a future EU regulatory framework;
- (4) Types of requirements;
- (5) Addressees;
- (6) Compliance and Enforcement;
- (7) Voluntary labelling for *No-High Risk AI Applications*;
- (8) Governance.

In April 2021, the European Commission presented its proposal for the EU AI Act, to which the Council of the EU adopted its common standing (December 2022). In June 2023, the European Parliament adopted its negotiating position on the AI Act, which, after numerous meetings, led to reaching the agreement on the proposal of the *Harmonized Rules on Artificial Intelligence (AI Act)* ([11]) and its Annexes [8]. These final documents are the ones we will discuss thoroughly in this paper.

BASIC IDEAS AND PRINCIPLES BEHIND THE act

The final Act's proposal is divided into several sections. The very first, introductory section extensively lists reasons for legally defining artificial intelligence, as well as expected topics that are to be covered by the Act, just like in the majority of other acts adopted jointly by EU Parliament and the Council (in the so called *codecision procedure*, first introduced in 1992

and, with the adoption of the Lisbon Treaty, renamed to the *ordinary legislative procedure*; since then it became the main decision-making procedure in the EU).

As stated at the beginning of the Act's proposal, *the purpose of this Regulation is to improve the functioning of the internal market by laying down a uniform legal framework in particular for the development, marketing and use of artificial intelligence in conformity with Union values. This Regulation pursues a number of overriding reasons of public interest, such as a high level of protection of health, safety and fundamental rights, and it ensures the free movement of AI-based goods and services cross-border, thus preventing Member States from imposing restrictions on the development, marketing and use of AI systems, unless explicitly authorised by this Regulation* ([11], recital 1).

The upcoming 89 points/paragraphs, all of which are interesting to analyze either independently or in conjunction with each other, lay the foundations of the EU's approach to AI.

The significant part of the Act is dedicated to protection of children: it is highlighted that children have specific rights based on the Article 24 of the EU Charter and based on the United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child, both of which require consideration of the children's vulnerabilities and provision of such protection, and care for their wellbeing, with no justification for revoking these rights when dealing with interactions with AI systems.

As this introductory section of the Act is condensed in examples, use cases, currently identified threats and benefits of using AI, we'll try to break the whole contents into several major fields. As some of introductory theses/guidelines/remarks were taken also to the normative part of the Act, here will not be referenced any particular article of the Act, as this would require a very extensive article. Instead of that, the intention is to give the overview of implications of the Act as a whole.

General provisions

The first several points of the Act's introduction define basic requirements for AI-based systems. Namely, after giving the definition of the AI systems, these requirements are set as mandatory:

- (1) the requirement to introduce common notion of AI system, in legal terms, in order to achieve legal certainty;
- (2) a need to ensure a level playing field and an effective protection of rights and freedoms of individuals across the EU;
- (3) a need to ensure a consistent and high level of protection of public interests, health, safety and fundamental rights;
- (4) a need to introduce a proportionate and effective set of binding requirements for AI systems.

And this is the part where things start to become more interesting.

The usage of AI by public institutions/law enforcement

The Act's proposal clearly identifies the problem when AI systems, which provide social scoring of natural persons for general purpose by public authorities or on their behalf, may lead to discriminatory outcomes

and the exclusion of certain groups. Actions by law enforcement authorities that involve certain uses of AI systems are characterised by a significant degree of power imbalance and may lead to surveillance, arrest or deprivation of a natural person's liberty, as well as other adverse impacts on fundamental rights. It is also noted that AI systems could produce adverse outcomes to health and safety of persons, in particular when these systems operate as components of some larger software products.

Having this in mind, the proposal implies several obligations for usage of AI systems for real-time biometric identification of natural persons in public spaces, for the purpose of law enforcement. One of the strongest requirements here is that these applications should be subject to an express and specific authorisation by a judicial authority, or by an independent administrative authority of a EU member state (i.e. in national law). Also, here applies the principle of ensuring that AI systems are used in a responsible and proportionate manner.

Mentioned ones, along with several other categories of AI systems, are classified as high-risk systems which have their unique, additional requirements. More on high-risk systems in the upcoming sections of this paper.

However, the Act brings one interesting standing when it comes to the national security, military and other defence-related applications of the AI. As stated in the recital -12a of the Act's introduction, which was added in revisioning process, *if and insofar AI systems are placed on the market, put into service, or used with or without modification of such systems for military, defence or national security purposes, those should be excluded from the scope of this Regulation regardless of which type of entity is carrying out those activities, such as whether it is a public or private entity.... As regards national security purposes, the exclusion is justified both by the fact that national security remains the sole responsibility of Member States ... and by the specific nature and operational needs of national security activities and specific national rules applicable to those activities. Nonetheless, if an AI system developed, placed on the market, put into service or used for military, defence or national security purposes is used outside those temporarily or permanently for other purposes (for example, civilian or humanitarian purposes, law enforcement or public security purposes), such a system would fall within the scope of this Regulation* ([11], recital -12a).

Specific risky usages of AI

Credit scoring , banking, public benefits, social protection

According to the Act, the classification of AI systems as high-risk AI systems should apply to those that, for example, assess the credit score or creditworthiness of natural persons, as such systems affect the ability of those persons to access financial resources or essential services, including but not limited to housing, electricity, and telecommunication services.

The use of AI systems for this purpose may result in discrimination of persons or groups and reinforce historical patterns of discrimination, such as those

based on racial or ethnic origins, disabilities, age, sexual orientation, or generate new forms of discriminatory impacts.

In view of the very limited scale of the impact and the existence of alternative solutions on the market, AI systems for the purpose of creditworthiness assessment and credit scoring should be exempted from this classification when deployed by small-scale providers for their own use.

Natural persons who apply for or receive public assistance benefits and services from public authorities are usually reliant on those benefits and services and in a precarious position vis-à-vis the competent authorities.

The use of AI systems for deciding whether such benefits and services should be refused, reduced, withdrawn or recovered by authorities may have a significant impact on persons' livelihood and may violate their fundamental rights, such as the right to social protection, non-discrimination, human dignity or an effective remedy.

Education and employment

AI systems used in education or vocational training should also be subject to careful scrutiny.

AI systems used in employment, workers management and access to self-employment, such as those for the recruitment and selection of persons, for making decisions on promotion and termination and for task allocation, monitoring or evaluation of persons in work-related contractual relationships, should be classified as high-risk systems, due to their potential impact on the rights and interests of persons or groups.

Judicial protection and rule of law

AI systems designed for the administration of justice, or to help in democratic processes, should also be classified as high-risk, given their possible significant impact on democracy, rule of law, individual freedoms as well as the right to an effective remedy and to a fair trial.

Specifically, to address the risks of potential biases, errors and opacity, it is suitable to classify as high-risk AI systems designed to assist judicial authorities in researching and interpreting facts and the law and in applying the law in concrete situation i.e. circumstances.

High-Risk AI Systems - general provisions

The Act proposal identifies the need to tighten the regulations around flexibility of high-risk AI systems. As defined in the Act, these systems should only be placed on the EU market or put into service if they comply with mandatory requirements.

High-risk AI systems, according to the proposal, should be designed and developed in a way that people can oversee their functioning. Also, the level of system's accuracy and metrics based on which it is determined should be explained to the users in an acceptable way. Furthermore, high-risk AI systems should be mandated to perform consistently, throughout their whole lifecycle, and meet appropriate levels of robustness, accuracy and cybersecurity.

The proposal also raises the question of accountability of high-risk AI system providers: *It is appropriate that a specific natural or legal person, defined as*

the provider, takes the responsibility for the placing on the market or putting into service of a high-risk AI system... The provider should establish a sound quality management system, ensure the accomplishment of the required conformity assessment procedure, draw up the relevant documentation and establish a robust post-market monitoring system ([11]).

High-risk AI systems, in order to ensure their trustworthiness and accuracy, should be subject to conformity checks/audits prior to putting them into service, as well as during the production period.

One of interesting requirements in the Act is that all high-risk AI systems should bear the CE marking, to indicate their conformity with the Act, so that they can move freely within the internal market.

Also, there is one registration requirement for providers of high-risk AI systems: they should be required to register their high-risk AI systems in a centralized EU database, in order to enable the European Commission to have the most accurate overview of all high-risk systems used in the EU.

System training

AI systems in general depend on high data quality for their performance and trustworthiness. This is especially true for techniques that are used in the training of models. The goal of the regulation should be to make sure that, especially the high-risk AI systems, work as intended and safely.

However, it is important to keep the balance here, so not to cause any discrimination that would be against the EU or member state laws. To achieve high data quality, proper data governance and management practices are needed. They apply to training, validation and testing data sets.

Access to high quality data is essential for the development of high-risk AI systems. The Act relates to certain actors who should be able to access and use such data. They include providers, notified bodies and other relevant entities, such as digital innovation hubs, testing experimentation facilities and researchers. They should use high quality data within their respective fields of activities. The European Commission has the obligation to establish so called *European common data spaces*, in order to facilitate data sharing between businesses and with government in the public interest ([11], recital 45).

These data spaces should provide trustful, accountable and non-discriminatory access to high quality data for the training, validation and testing of AI systems. For instance, in health sector, the *European health data space* will enable non-discriminatory access to health data and the training of artificial intelligence algorithms on those datasets. It will do so in a privacy-preserving, secure, timely, transparent and trustworthy manner, and with an appropriate institutional governance. Relevant competent authorities, such as sectoral ones, may also support the provision of high-quality data for the training, validation and testing of AI systems.

Interaction AI – human

AI systems that are designed to virtually talk to people or make new content may impose risks of faking

or tricking people (deceiving them), no matter if they are classified as high-risk or not.

The solution proposed in the Act is that all these systems should be clear about what they are doing, regardless of being high-risk AI systems or not. For example, people should know that they are talking to an AI system, unless it is obviously clear from the situation context and the way they are using it.

As prescribed in the Act, people should know when they are facing an emotion recognition system or a biometric categorisation system. Also, users who use an AI system to make or change image, audio or video content that looks like real people, places or events and which, as a result, could fool someone to think they are real, should be obliged to notify, in a clear way, that the content is fake or changed by using AI systems.

Relations to personal data protection regulations

This topic is covered in later added recital 58a of the Act's proposal, which states: *It is appropriate to clarify that this Regulation does not affect the obligations of providers and users of AI systems in their role as data controllers or processors stemming from Union law on the protection of personal data in so far as the design, the development or the use of AI systems involves the processing of personal data. It is also appropriate to clarify that data subjects continue to enjoy all the rights and guarantees awarded to them by such Union law, including the rights related to solely automated individual decision-making, including profiling...* ([11], recital 58a).

Requirements towards technical robustness, standardization and cybersecurity

As defined in the Act, *standardisation should play a key role to provide technical solutions to providers to ensure compliance with this Regulation* ([11], recital 61).

The Act further requires that the high-risk AI system should have the capacity to withstand and recover from any hazards arising from its own deficiencies (such as errors, faults, inconsistencies, unforeseen circumstances) and from any hostile acts that may endanger the integrity of the AI system and cause detrimental or unwanted consequences.

The lack of adequate safeguards against these hazards may result in adverse effects on the safety or the fundamental rights of the affected parties, for instance due to inaccurate decisions or incorrect or prejudiced outputs produced by the AI system.

The security of the AI system and its resistance to any modifications of its purpose, conduct, output or impairment of its security attributes by malevolent actors who take advantage of the system's weaknesses are essential.

The AI system may be, just like any other computer system, subject to cyberattacks that target specific resources, such as training data sets (*data poisoning*) or trained models (*adversarial attacks*), or that exploit flaws in the AI system's digital resources or the supporting ICT infrastructure. Hence, the function of cybersecurity in terms of AI, especially high-risk AI, is of great importance ([1], [14]).

KEY NORMATIVE SOLUTIONS AND APPROACHES

When discussing normative part of the Act proposal, it can be noticed that it establishes a horizontal level of protection, comprising a risk-based categorization, to guarantee that AI systems that have a low probability of causing severe fundamental rights breaches or other significant hazards are exempt from those more strict rules. AI systems posing only minimal risk would be subject to very mild transparency requirements, such as the requirement for revealing that the content was produced by AI, so users can decide on further use of that particular system.

The Act proposal introduces several new elements in comparison to the initial proposal of the Commission, which can be briefly outlined as follows:

- regulations on general-purpose AI models of high impact that may pose systemic risk in the future, in addition to high-risk AI systems;
- an improved system of governance with some authority to enforce at the EU level;
- a broader list of prohibitions with an exception for the use of remote biometric identification by law enforcement authorities in public spaces, under certain conditions;
- enhanced protection of rights by requiring deployers of high-risk AI systems to perform a fundamental rights impact assessment before deploying an AI system.

To enter the EU market, a variety of high-risk AI systems would be permitted, but they would have to meet a set of conditions and responsibilities. The legislators have made these conditions more clear and modified them so that they are easier to implement technically and less demanding for stakeholders to follow, such as concerning the data quality, or with respect to the technical documentation that SMEs should prepare to show that their high-risk AI systems meet the conditions.

The proposal also deals with responsibilities of both AI providers and users. Namely, this is stated in the official communication from the EU: *Since AI systems are developed and distributed through complex value chains, the compromise agreement includes changes clarifying the allocation of responsibilities and roles of the various actors in those chains, in particular providers and users of AI systems. It also clarifies the relationship between responsibilities under the AI Act and responsibilities that already exist under other legislation, such as the relevant EU data protection or sectorial legislation* ([3]).

The Proposed Act adopts a “*technology neutral*”, risk-based approach in which AI systems are classified and regulated based on risk to citizens, individually or collectively. Risk categories include

- “*unacceptable risk*” (i.e. these AI systems shall be prohibited in the EU);
- “*high-risk*” (these will be the systems subject to stringent rules);
- “*limited risk*” (systems with transparency requirements), and
- “*low or minimal risk*” (minimal to no regulation needed).

AI systems with unacceptable risks are those for which use contravenes European values and principles,

including, as stated, “*human dignity, freedom, democracy, equality, the rule of law, and respect for human rights*” ([14]).

Examples of AI systems that would create “unacceptable risk” if deployed include

- *biometric categorization systems that rely on sensitive characteristics (race, sexual orientation, political, religious, philosophical beliefs);*
- *untargeted scraping of facial images from the internet or CCTV footage to create facial recognition databases;*
- *emotion recognition in the workplace and educational institutions;*
- *social scoring based on social behavior or personal characteristics;*
- *AI systems that manipulate human behavior to circumvent their free will; and*
- *AI used to exploit the vulnerabilities of people due to their age, disability, social or economic situation* ([14]).

“High-risk” systems include those AI systems that negatively affect safety or fundamental rights. This tier is proposed to be divided into two subcategories:

(1) AI systems used for products (e.g. toys, aviation, medical devices); and

(2) software-focused AI systems leveraged by particular critical industries or public services including infrastructure, education, employment, law enforcement, border control, and assistance in legal interpretations of the law.

For high-risk systems, the Act requires entities to mitigate risks, conduct a fundamental rights impact assessment, use high-quality data sets and ensure capability for ongoing human oversight. Citizens will also have the right to file complaints with respect to high-risk AI systems, based on system's impact on their rights ([6], [14]).

General purpose AI systems (GPAI) designed to interact with humans, such as chatbots or other assistants, are considered “limited risk.” GPAIs are proposed to be subject to transparency obligations, such as notifying the public when interacting with chatbots and/or biometric or emotion recognition systems.

Entities that are involved in the training of foundational or general purpose models for the use of other parties, will have the obligation to provide information about the nature and source of the data that they used to train these models.

Entities that create AI systems that have generative capabilities, such as ChatGPT, will also have the responsibility to disclose that the generated content is not human-made and to ensure that their systems do not produce any content that is illegal or that infringes on the intellectual property rights.

The Act intends to encourage innovation and, in the same time, respect people’s rights and democracy. This is for sure not an easy task: some privacy and human rights groups say that the Act is not strict enough to keep people safe from all the possible effects of AI. Some schools and businesses are, on the other side, worried that the Act might slow down their research and development.

In order to at least partially overcome previously mentioned challenges, it has been clarified in the Act that AI regulatory sandboxes, which are supposed to establish a controlled environment for the development, testing and validation of innovative AI systems, should allow for testing of innovative AI systems in real world conditions.

Penalties

A new agreement has been reached on the penalties for breaking the AI Act. The proposal sets the fines as a percentage of the company's global annual turnover or a fixed amount, whichever is higher. The highest fines of €35 million or 7% will apply to the use of banned AI applications, such as those that manipulate human behaviour. The fines will be lower for other violations, such as failing to meet the AI law's requirements or providing false information. The proposal also introduces more lenient fines for small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) and start-ups, to avoid discouraging innovation.

The Act also clarifies the rights of individuals and organisations to report any breaches of the AI law to the authorities. The authorities will have to follow specific procedures to handle the complaints and ensure that the AI Act is continuously enforced.

Conclusion

The Act is a new global standard for how to use AI in a safe and ethical way. It aims to balance the benefits of AI, such as making things faster and smarter, with the risks, such as losing jobs, spreading fake news and threatening security. The Act is the first of its kind to regulate AI across different sectors and situations.

The Act is not finally adopted yet, but its contents is more or less definite. The proposed rules are based on how AI systems are used and how risky they are. The Act defines what AI systems are and sorts them into different categories with different rules. Some AI systems that are too dangerous would be banned. Many AI systems that are risky would be allowed, but they would have to follow certain standards and rules to enter the EU market. Some AI systems that are not very risky would only have to be transparent about how they work.

Some organizations might want to create a new job or role of "AI regulatory officer" to make sure that their business follows the rules of the AI Act when it becomes a law. An AI regulatory officer would check that the AI systems are used safely inside the organization and have protections when sold to others ([1], [19]).

The new regulation will be closely watched globally. It will impact not just big AI companies like Google, Meta, Microsoft and OpenAI, but also other businesses that use AI for education, health care or, for example, banking.

Governments are also using more AI for things like criminal justice and public benefits. However, it is not clear how the Act will be enforced. The Act will need regulators from 27 countries and new experts when, on the other side, money governments have is low.

Previous EU legislation, the General Data Protection Regulation, has been criticized for being unevenly enforced.

»The E.U.'s regulatory prowess is under question«, said Kris Shrishak ([18]), an expert at the Irish Council for Civil Liberties who helped European lawmakers with the Act. As he pointed out, the Act will be useless without strong enforcement.

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